

INTERNAL ASSESSMENT

ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF PET

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April 2022

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NOMENCLATURE AND ACRONYMS

Acronym/Symbol	Description
PET / PETE	Polyethylene terephthalate
NaOH	Sodium hydroxide
H ₂ SO ₄	Sulfuric acid
Na ₂ SO ₄	Sodium sulfate
EG	Ethylene glycol (monomer)
TPA	Terephthalic acid (monomer)
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
n	Number of repeating units in a polymer chain
M	Molarity (moles per liter)
g	Grams
°C	Degrees Celsius
r	Pearson Correlation Coefficient
R^2 / r^2	Coefficient of determination
SD	Standard Deviation
H_0	Null Hypothesis
H_a	Alternative Hypothesis

1 INTRODUCTION

This internal assessment presents traditional laboratory experimentation and analysis on the alkaline hydrolysis of plastic, a recent method for converting plastic waste into usable monomers.

Plastic waste is a significant global issue that dangerously threatens the Earth and human health. Currently, only 9% of the 300 million tons of plastic produced annually is reused. Developing a method to recycle plastic on a large scale is essential to resolving this critical problem once and for all.

According to the WWF and FAO, ghost fishing gear made of polyolefins is the deadliest form of marine plastic, despite comprising only 10% of total ocean plastic. Designed specifically to capture animals, this gear continues to entrap marine life indefinitely after being disposed of in the ocean. The destruction of marine mammals and fish disrupts the fragile ecosystem that supports phytoplankton—microorganisms that use chlorophyll for photosynthesis and produce 70% of the planet's oxygen as a byproduct. This oxygen is a fundamental requirement for our existence.

I have personally always been concerned about the global plastic crisis. For this reason, I have always acted in my own small way for the planet's well-being, participating in several Fridays For Future events in Milan to raise public awareness about this tragic problem and to reduce my personal plastic consumption to the minimum. I hold great hope for this promising process, which can provide a new plastic recycling method and ensure a future for life on Earth.

2 RESEARCH QUESTION

How do various concentrations of the base sodium hydroxide (NaOH)—5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25%—over a fixed 24-hour period affect the mass (grams) of terephthalic acid ($C_8H_6O_4$) and ethylene glycol ($(CH_2OH)_2$) monomers formed from polyethylene terephthalate ($(C_{10}H_8O_4)_n$) in an alkaline hydrolysis reaction?

3 BACKGROUND INFORMATION

Hydrolysis, a branch of depolymerization processes, is a chemical reaction between hydrogen cations (H^+) or hydroxyl anions (OH^-) and a material that breaks its long polymer chains into their original identical molecules, called monomers. The organic material used here is a substance composed of carbon (C) chains and other elements that can be reversed from its polymer form back into its original monomeric state, which can then be transformed again through polymerization (the hope for the future).

In this internal assessment, the material used is a polyolefin—a class of synthetic resins prepared by the polymerization of olefins—the process of chemically combining the monomers of a hydrocarbon into a polymer.

The subset of polyolefins involved in this experiment is polyethylene terephthalate ($(C_{10}H_8O_4)_n$), also known as PET or PETE. This polymer consists of the monomers $C_8H_6O_4$ and $(CH_2OH)_2$ repeated " n " times in the chain, as shown in Figure 1. Polypropylene was avoided in this study due to its higher chemical resistance.

The alkaline hydrolysis reaction takes place in a flat-bottomed cylindrical container, where the PET interacts with the strong base sodium hydroxide (NaOH) without external

Figure 3: TPA monomer ($C_8H_6O_4$)

aids or accelerators such as heat or pressure. Over time, the base breaks down the chemical bonds of the polymer through contact with hydroxyl anions (OH^-).

Subsequently, the strong acid sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) is added via a volumetric pipette into the beaker to partially neutralize the system. The solution is then filtered using a ceramic funnel, and the remaining PET is collected and washed to remove the sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4) salt formed. This process allows for a conclusive analysis of the change in mass (grams) of the polymers successfully depolymerized into monomers, as shown in Figure 4.

I must specify that this experiment does not utilize PETase enzyme catalysts, heat energy, or high pressure (which makes the complete depolymerization of PET strips impossible). Instead, I am attempting to simulate industrial alkaline hydrolysis on a smaller scale at room temperature ($20^\circ C$) to isolate and analyze the process and determine if there is a statistically relevant result.

Figure 4: Alkaline hydrolysis of PET

Prior to the development of these chemical processes, plastic was recycled only mechanically. However, mechanical recycling is often more expensive than producing new plastic from raw materials. A more attractive system was needed, and chemical recycling offers a cost-effective and efficient alternative.

The most effective process for chemical recycling is hydrolysis; indeed, all previous methods lacked efficiency or were not as environmentally friendly. For instance, feedstock recycling processes (gasification, pyrolysis, and hydrothermal treatment) transform polymers into usable fuel but require high-energy burners that produce further CO_2 and other pollutants.

Regarding other chemical recycling processes, scientists have developed glycolysis, methanolysis, ammonolysis, and aminolysis. The most common and significant methods are hydrolysis and glycolysis. This internal assessment focuses on alkaline hydrolysis due to its simplicity, effectiveness, and prevalence.

If the materials reacted perfectly (as they would on an industrial scale), the formula for the alkaline hydrolysis of PET would be:

However, due to the simplified laboratory scale, the materials did not fully react and the systems were only partially neutralized, leaving unreacted $NaOH$, H_2SO_4 , and PET leftovers alongside the final products EG, TPA, and Na_2SO_4 .

4 HYPOTHESES

Null hypothesis (H_0): Increasing the concentration of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) will have no effect on the final mass (grams) of polyethylene terephthalate ($C_{10}H_8O_4$)_n in an alkaline hydrolysis reaction.

Alternative hypothesis (H_a): Increasing the concentration of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) will have a significant effect on the final mass (grams) of polyethylene terephthalate ($C_{10}H_8O_4$)_n in an alkaline hydrolysis reaction.

4.1 Key variables

Independent variable	The concentration of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25% in an approximately 100 milliliters solution containing water as a solvent.
Dependent variable	The mass in grams of the remaining PET ($C_{10}H_8O_4$) _n after an alkaline hydrolysis reaction.
Controlled variable + Value	Method of control
Mass of PET - approximately 5 grams	The mass of PET strips in each experiment was controlled using an Ainsworth Model 100A Scale, subtracting the strips to approximately reach 5 grams of mass to put in each beaker.
Volume of sulfuric acid - approximately 100 mL	The volume of sulfuric acid in the experiment was controlled using a 5 milliliters volumetric pipette. Each system was provided with the same molarity of sulfuric acid at 18 molar to mix with the PET and the sodium hydroxide.
Time 24 hours	The time to let the alkaline hydrolysis of PET occur was set to 24 hours for each of the 25 trials performed.
Temperature 20°C	The temperature of the surroundings of the systems wasn't modified, indeed the alkaline hydrolysis reaction had occurred at a stable room temperature of 20°C.
Scientific balance Ainsworth Model 100A Scale 1 item	The mass change of the PET strips was measured with the use of the scientific balance Ainsworth Model 100A Scale for each of the 25 trials performed.

5 MATERIALS

The experimenter needs the following materials to successfully conduct the alkaline hydrolysis reaction of polyethylene terephthalate ($C_{10}H_8O_4$)_n:

- Approximately 125 grams of polyethylene terephthalate ($C_{10}H_8O_4$)_n strips of roughly 1.5×4 cm (cut from soft drink plastic bottles).
- 125 milliliters of 18 molar sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4).
- Approximately 2500 milliliters of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) at different concentrations to divide in 5×500 milliliters (5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25%).
- 5 volumetric flasks (to contain the various concentrations of the base).
- 25 beakers of 300 or 500 milliliters (the size is not fundamental as long as the plastic is completely submerged into the base).
- 25 beakers or volumetric flasks (to divide the various concentrations of the base and facilitate the pouring).
- A ventilation system.
- A glass stirrer rod.
- A 5 milliliters volumetric pipette (to pour the acid inside the beakers).
- A ceramic funnel.
- A strainer.
- Tongs.
- Ainsworth Model 100A Scale, or every other scientific balance.
- 25 filter papers.
- A sheet of paper.
- A pen.
- A timer.

6 METHODOLOGY

In order to complete a successful alkaline hydrolysis reaction of polyethylene terephthalate ($C_{10}H_8O_4$)_n the experimenter has to follow the following methodology proceedings:

Research Preparation & Background Information:

1. Do research on plastic.
2. Do research on the effects of plastic on planet Earth.
3. Do research on the most used plastic.
4. Do research on polyethylene terephthalate ($C_{10}H_8O_4$)_n (PET).
5. Do research on chemical methods to recycle PET.
6. Do research on alkaline hydrolysis of PET.

Materials organization and preparation:

7. Gather all the necessary materials for the alkaline hydrolysis of PET.
8. Look for soft drink plastic bottles with written PET on the bottom (sometimes shown as PETE).
9. Cut the PET soft drink bottles into strips of approximately 1.5×4 cm.
10. Label 25 beakers with mass (grams), the material contained, various concentrations of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) (in %), and the number of trials while step 11 is being carried out.
11. Divide, mass, and organize the PET with an Ainsworth Model 100A Scale (or any other scientific balance).
12. Organize 5 different lines inside the ventilation system based on the various concentrations of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) (5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25%) and the 5 different trials for every concentration.
13. Divide approximately 500 milliliters in 5×100 milliliters of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) of every concentration percentage into beakers or volumetric flasks with the support of tongs (in order to facilitate the pouring, the size of the container is not fundamental and does not affect the experiment).

Alkaline Hydrolysis of PET, Stage 1 - NaOH bath for depolymerization:

14. Start a timer right after step 15 is executed.
15. Pour the various concentrations of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) prepared in step 13 into the 25 beakers of 300 or 500 milliliters containing PET previously divided following step 12.
16. Slightly mix the content with the glass stirrer rod.
17. Prepare and label the 25 filter papers.
18. Wait 24 hours.

Alkaline Hydrolysis of PET, Stage 2 - Partial Neutralization of the systems:

19. Pour 5 milliliters of 18 molar sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) with the 5 milliliters volumetric pipette into every beaker containing the PET and the sodium hydroxide (NaOH).
20. Slightly mix the content with the glass stirrer rod.
21. Filter the content of every beaker with the ceramic funnel and put the PET remains in the labeled 25 filter papers prepared in step 17.
22. Wait until the remains of the salt sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4) product crystallize on the PET remains.
23. After the salt sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4) crystals are visible, gently wash the PET remains under a sink with the use of a strainer (to avoid losing pieces).

24. Let the PET dry for approximately 24 hours.

Conclusion:

25. Mass the PET remains with the same scientific balance used in step 11 (in my case an Ainsworth Model 100A Scale).

26. Draw scientific and statistical conclusions from the experiment.

7 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

There are no ethical issues regarding this experiment. The procedures were conducted following scientific ethics, without harming anyone or anything during the operation.

8 ENVIRONMENTAL CONSIDERATIONS

The alkaline hydrolysis of PET may produce toxic gases and liquids, as well as plastic remnants that are detrimental to the environment. To mitigate these issues, I handled the gases and liquids produced from the reaction within a properly closed ventilation system. Regarding the plastic remnants, I disposed of them in the appropriate PET recycling bins to ensure they reach a recycling center for a second life.

9 SAFETY PROTOCOLS

In the alkaline hydrolysis reaction of the polyethylene terephthalate $(C_{10}H_8O_4)_n$ the experimenter will have to deal with the following dangers:

- Strong base liquids.
- Strong acid liquids.
- Potential toxic fumes are created by the reactions.
- Potential burning temperatures are created by the reactions.

In order to contrast the dangers above, the experimenter will have to use the following precautions and solutions:

- Protective laboratory goggles.
- Acids and bases resistant protective gloves.
- A ventilation system.
- The support of the tongs.

10 ANALYSIS

10.1 Raw Data

Raw Data for Mass (grams) from the initial PET strips (initial mass) to final PET remains (final mass): Raw data gathered on the mass of PET strips divided and measured approximately for 5 grams in each of the 25 trials performed with the use of the scientific balance Ainsworth Model 100A Scale, before and after the alkaline hydrolysis reaction occurred in 24 hours.

Table 1: Raw Data: Mass in grams (g) ($\pm 0.00001g$)

NaOH %	TRIAL 1		TRIAL 2		TRIAL 3		TRIAL 4		TRIAL 5	
	Initial	Final								
5%	5.0398	4.6014	5.0453	4.7115	5.0513	4.7137	5.0495	4.7125	5.0563	4.7326
10%	5.0614	4.7392	5.0795	4.7343	5.0552	4.7234	5.0481	4.7118	5.0457	4.7135
15%	5.0477	4.7153	5.0718	4.7271	5.0579	4.6838	5.0444	4.6571	5.0675	4.6778
20%	5.0619	4.6737	5.0514	4.6573	4.6325	5.0377	5.0517	4.6478	5.0749	4.6746
25%	5.0699	4.6768	5.0479	4.6474	5.0588	4.6412	5.0729	4.6766	5.0498	4.6313

10.2 Processed Data

Change in Mass (grams) between the initial PET strips and the final PET remains: grams (g) ($\pm 0.00001g$)

Processed data on the change in mass (grams) between the initial PET strips and the final PET remains collected in the 25 trials performed after the alkaline hydrolysis reaction had occurred. The mass change is equal to the EG and TPA monomers successfully depolymerized from the polymer polyethylene terephthalate ($C_{10}H_8O_4$) $_n$.

Table 2: Processed Data: Mass Change (g)

NaOH %	TRIAL 1	TRIAL 2	TRIAL 3	TRIAL 4	TRIAL 5	Std Dev
5%	0.4384	0.3338	0.3376	0.3370	0.3237	0.0478
10%	0.3222	0.3452	0.3318	0.3363	0.3322	0.0311
15%	0.3324	0.3447	0.3741	0.3873	0.3897	0.0387
20%	0.3882	0.3941	0.4052	0.4039	0.4003	0.0329
25%	0.3931	0.4005	0.4176	0.3963	0.4185	0.0424

10.3 Data Processing & Statistical Analysis

The scatterplot above shows the relationship between the explanatory variable of the various concentrations of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and the response variable of the average mass change of PET (± 1 Standard Deviation) in an alkaline hydrolysis reaction.

The graph clearly shows a strong positive linear association between the independent and dependent variables with no clusters, confirmed by the Pearson Correlation Coefficient $r = 0.875874821896988$ found using the software Google Sheets.

It was also found that the coefficient of determination r^2 is equal to 0.76715670363308, implying a strong predictability in the variability of the y-axis of the dependent variable

Figure 5: Concentration of NaOH VS Average mass change of PET (± 1 SD)

(mass change of PET) compared to the x-axis of the independent variable (various concentrations of NaOH) that is accounted for by the least-squares regression line.

Yet an outlier in regression is present at a 10% concentration of sodium hydroxide (NaOH), indeed its value does not follow the pattern of the data and has a larger residual compared to the trendline for average mass change.

Because the r value is not equal to 0 and the P-value is equal to 0.000359853314641244, which is far less than the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$, I confidently reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and conclude that there is sufficient evidence to state that increasing the concentration of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) has an effect on the final mass (grams) of polyethylene terephthalate ($C_{10}H_8O_4$)_n in an alkaline hydrolysis reaction (H_a).

In formula:

$$r = \frac{\sum(x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y - \bar{y})^2}}$$

Interpretation of Correlation Coefficient Value (r):

- -1: Perfectly negative
- -0.8: Strongly negative
- -0.5: Moderately negative
- -0.2: Weakly negative
- 0: No association
- 0.2: Weakly positive
- 0.5: Moderately positive
- 0.8: Strongly positive
- 1: Perfectly positive

11 QUALITATIVE OBSERVATIONS

Throughout the experiment, it was easily noticeable that as the concentration of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) increased, the PET strips looked more degraded. Indeed they seemed far more deformed and dulled at higher concentration percentages, a clear sign of successful depolymerization occurred.

The difference between the various concentrations in the systems, which looked transparent, was not visible to the naked eye, yet I felt a considerable difference when I was pouring the sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) to partially neutralize the systems: higher concentrations of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) reacted more aggressively than lower ones, creating more dangerous splashes and white salt sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4) crystals on the PET remains.

The passages from the scientific balance to the beakers, to the ceramic funnel, to the filter papers, to the wash, back to the scientific balance for the final mass were very risky and required particular attention and care in order not to drop or lose the PET strips remains and cause an enormous error in the data.

Figure 6: Image 1-25 labeled beakers containing PET and NaOH || Image 2 - salt Na_2SO_4 crystals on PET remains

12 IMPACT OF UNCERTAINTY & ERRORS

Due to the extremely low uncertainty equal to grams (g)($\pm 0.00001g$) of the scientific balance Ainsworth Model 100A Scale used to measure the mass (grams) change of the PET strips before and after the alkaline hydrolysis, the impact of uncertainty and errors is really weak and the data can be considered reliable.

Therefore the calculation of the uncertainty: Formula % uncertainty \rightarrow (Uncertainty / Measurement collected) $\cdot 100$

- 5% NaOH $\rightarrow (\pm 0.00001 \div 0.3541) \cdot 100 = 0.0028\%$
- 10% NaOH $\rightarrow (\pm 0.00001 \div 0.3335) \cdot 100 = 0.0030\%$
- 15% NaOH $\rightarrow (\pm 0.00001 \div 0.3656) \cdot 100 = 0.0027\%$
- 20% NaOH $\rightarrow (\pm 0.00001 \div 0.3983) \cdot 100 = 0.0025\%$
- 25% NaOH $\rightarrow (\pm 0.00001 \div 0.4052) \cdot 100 = 0.0025\%$

13 STRENGTHS, LIMITATIONS, & IMPROVEMENTS

During the completion of this Internal Assessment on the alkaline hydrolysis of PET I found several strengths, limitations, and possible improvements:

Strengths:

- I used PET from the same soft drink plastic bottles (PET), this allowed me to eliminate the error related to the possible different thicknesses of the PET strips.
- I was successfully able to divide, mass, and label the PET strips amounts relatively precisely, thanks to the use of the scientific balance Ainsworth Model 100A Scale.
- I was successfully able to reproduce an industrial-type setting into a much easier and smaller system to replicate the alkaline hydrolysis of PET in a smaller manner and environment.
- I had a statistically relevant result even if I didn't use any catalyst or accelerator (such as PETase enzyme catalysts, high temperature, and strong pressure).

Limitations:

- There is a lack of information on the alkaline hydrolysis of PET or any other chemical process to recycle plastic on the internet due to its novelty and experimentation state.
- I didn't use catalysts or other accelerators so the PET strips weren't completely depolymerized.
- I had to use different sizes (300 and 500 milliliters) beakers because of their availability in the laboratory (yet it should not affect the outcomes of the experiment as long as all the strips are able to be submerged in the base).

- After I filtered the PET strips to let them dry and record their final mass, I had to wash them twice with the support of a strainer, because the salt sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4) strongly crystallized on them. This was very dangerous because I risked losing or dropping the PET strip remains, and invalidating the entire project.

Improvements:

- Purchase beakers of the same size in order to reduce to the minimum the possibility of an error.
- Purchase PET pellets instead of hand-cut strips to remarkably reduce the amount of manual labor (approximately 2 hours and 30 minutes of cut), have very precisely divided amounts, and decrease the errors.
- If possible, use heat energy, pressure, and/or PETase enzyme catalysts in order to facilitate, speed up, and improve the reaction.
- Collect information on alkaline hydrolysis of PET directly from an expert or a recommended source because of the lack of information on the internet.

14 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the alkaline hydrolysis of plastic using sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) is a very promising process for depolymerizing polyethylene terephthalate ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$)_n back into its monomers—ethylene glycol (CH_2OH)₂ and terephthalic acid ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{O}_4$)—for recycling. This is a valuable operation, especially if conducted on an industrial scale with the support of heat and catalysts to fully depolymerize the PET wasted daily. As discussed, ghost fishing gear is a major threat to our planet, and we must act now.

I can conclude that the association found supports my alternative hypothesis. The null hypothesis was rejected due to the strong positive linear association between NaOH concentration and the average mass change of the PET strips. As concentration increases on the y-axis, the mass change also increases on the x-axis, except for the 10% outlier. I am confident in these results as the scatterplot shows a strong linear association with an r value of 0.87587 and an R^2 of 0.76716.

Furthermore, I can infer that the association found in this experiment implies causation between the independent and dependent variables. There is a theoretical correlation between varying concentrations of NaOH and the mass of monomers formed from PET in an alkaline hydrolysis reaction.

15 FURTHER EXTENSION

This experiment has promising further extensions, connections with the real world, and bonds with the fight against the global plastic issue. If I was able to use industrial machinery I would have had the precious opportunity to significantly carry out the alkaline hydrolysis of PET for the sake of humanity and the planet Earth. Indeed with an industrial level system and advanced means of supplies, the alkaline hydrolysis of PET is extremely improved. Such as the presence of strong pressure and high heat energy that guarantee a

rapid acceleration of the reaction, and PETase enzymes catalysts that ensure an almost completely or fully depolymerized recycled batch of PET.

Above all, the most important and relevant extension would be to collect the TPA and the EG monomers successfully depolymerized from the PET after the alkaline hydrolysis in order to produce 100% recycled plastic again through polymerization, my hope for the future.

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